

PHYSICAL SCIENCES

THE PHYSICAL ABILITY TO BRING A PERSON WHO HAS DIED, FOR EXAMPLE AS A RESULT OF AN ACCIDENT OR A CRIME, BACK TO LIFE¹⁰

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Abstract

In the article it is suggested that due to the fast (faster than the Earth rotates) movement on the Earth through time zones to carry out accessible to people travelling (for example, by plane) both in the past and in the future time. An example of realisation of such time travel routes is given, allowing to bring back to life people who died as a result of an accident or criminal humans activity.

Keywords: arrow of time, corrected version of the special theory of relativity, anti-time, internal time, external time, time zones, time travels.

1. Introduction

The title of the article may be perplexing. What can physics have to do with bringing a person back to life? Especially not in science fiction, but in serious science? But, it turns out, it can, although this serious science itself does not agree with this opinion.

The fact is that it is possible to bring a person back to life by travelling through time. But the possibility of travelling in time, except for some purely theoretical situations - in the twin paradox of the special theory of relativity (SRT), as a result of teleportations in quantum mechanics and in some other exotic theoretical situations - in practical human activity is denied by physics even in the distant future).

However, this article provides descriptions of useful new human activities that are physically already feasible on Earth now using time travel to the past and into the future.

2. Proof of the physical reality of time travel on Earth is already in the present day

Here are a couple of quotes that illustrate the current state of understanding of the problem of time. *"Time is the most frequently used word in the English language and the third most frequently used word in Russian. It is also frequently used in all other languages, too, because synchronizing actions in time is as important as coordinating them in space. Without knowing the exact time, it is impossible to organize your life and plan it in advance. If in ancient times you could rely on natural cycles and an internal sense of time, then in our days you must constantly have a watch or a phone with you. Time is the most important of the abstract concepts that we pronounce every day. Every thinking person has thought about the problem of time at least once in his life. And a huge amount of philosophical and scientific literature has been written on this topic. Nevertheless, no one can say with certainty even what time is."* [1]

And here is what Stephen William Hawking writes about this [2]: *"In ordinary life, there is a huge difference between moving forward and backward in time. Imagine that a cup of water falls from a table and*

breaks into pieces. If you film this fall, then when you watch the film, it will immediately become clear whether the film is running forward or backward. If it is running backward, then we will see how the fragments lying on the floor suddenly come together and, having formed a whole cup, jump onto the table. And you will be able to claim that the film was running backward, because in ordinary life this does not happen. Otherwise, all the faience factories would have to be closed."

This phenomenon, known as the 'arrow of time', is one of the most surprising problems in physics. The name 'arrow of time' was proposed by the British physicist Sir Arthur Stanley Eddington in the early XX century [3]. And all our life experience, as it would seem, confirms the truth of this concept.

But the corrected version of SRT [4]-[12], in which a new concept of 'anti-time' has appeared, induces this life experience to be corrected. Indeed, if we assume that soon travelling through the expanses of universes and antiverse of the hidden Multiverse will become possible for people on Earth, then time travel [13] will also become possible, both in the past and in the future.

Moreover, time travel on Earth is already not only possible now, but also exists, although it is not used [14]-[25]. And since they are much easier and cheaper than in space, we will consider them. At the same time we will need two new concepts - internal (or biological) time of a human being and external time of his environment. And these two times have different properties. Human biological time cannot flow backwards. That is, a person cannot return to his youth or childhood. But the situation in the external environment in which a human being is, as a result of human activity, can change in the most incredible way. And in this external environment it is already possible to move both to the future and to the past time. And even short-term movements in time can be very useful. For example, if you get an opportunity to look into the future time for a short time,

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you can make a better choice in the present. Or by travelling to the past, it is possible to correct something in the present time.

And such external time for people on Earth exists. It's known to everyone. These are 24 time zones, which are caused by the Earth's rotation around its axis. Moving through them in space, people also move in time. And depending on the direction of movement in space - to the west or to the east - they can move both to the past and to the future time. This is well known to everyone, but it has not been used in creative human activity so far.

But this is a free resource presented to us by nature to solve the problem of time travel, which is not difficult to use if you have an aeroplane (because you need to travel faster than the Earth rotates). Indeed, to travel 24 hours into the past, for example, you only need to move westwards by 24 time zones. To move into the future, you would have to do the same thing, but only by travelling east. All this is not difficult to do. It is also necessary to take into account that the closer to the pole - it does not matter which one, northern or southern - the transport route of time travelers will run, the less biological time will be required to cross one time zone. Therefore, it is more advantageous to lay it closer to the poles (for example, at a distance of 100-1000 km from the pole around the pole). But since the internal biological time in ordinary human activity for almost all people (who do not fly) flows much faster than external time, external time is usually not taken into account by people. Such a concept is still not even present in col-

loquial speech. And although millions of people are already travelling through time by flying planes, it has never occurred to anyone until now that there is any benefit to be gained from time travel. But it turns out that it is possible.

3. How the laws of physics can be used to bring a person who died as a result of a crime back to life.

Let's consider one of these situations. And from the analysis of this situation it will become clear how to act in other situations.

For example, let's assume that in one of the South American countries (this option will be convenient to explain, since this country is located near the South Pole) the president is killed. This situation is illustrated by Fig. 1, which shows the trajectories of movement in time:

- the President of this country;
- the head of the security service;
- and all the other people – both those who saw the assassination attempt on the president and those who did not.

Therefore, the temporal trajectory of the President's life ("a" in Fig. 1) ends with this murder (this moment is shown by a large black dot). And upon seeing this (shown by the thin black arrow), the head of the security service ("b" in Fig. 1) begins to act – he organises the President's delivery to the nearest military hospital, organises security, instructs him to report to the press that the President is alive, and instructs his staff to strictly prevent any leakage of information that the President has already died.

Fig. 1. Time travel routes of the President (in red) and the head of the security service (in blue), ensuring the return of the President to life after an assassination attempt on him, as well as the rest of the inhabitants of the Earth (in green). Solid lines show their movements on the surface of the Earth, and dotted lines show the movements of the head of the security service on an airplane through time zones.

Then the head of the security service gets on an aeroplane ("c" in Fig. 1) and, having flown around Antarctica through 24 time zones, lands in the past time at the same aerodrome from which he took off in the present time. Outside time for him has changed into the past by 24 hours, and the internal biological time of his space-time journey, i.e. the flight time, has changed, for example, by 10 hours. Consequently, the head of the security service flew back in time 14 hours before the assassination attempt on the President. And therefore, during the remaining time ("d" in Fig. 1) he has time to

take the necessary measures to save the President and neutralise the criminal (or criminals). And so for this country, its President - a real living President at that - could be saved¹¹.

However, as Figure 1 shows, the situation is still unresolved. Firstly, after the assassination attempt, which was witnessed by many people, the President in this situation turns out to be not only alive but also fully healthy as a result of the activities of the head of the security service. However, even Presidents do not recover so quickly. And to explain to the people how the President was brought back to life is to be inexpedient,

¹¹ Perhaps President Kennedy could have been saved in a similar fashion

as it is not known how it will be perceived by them. However, this can be remedied: the President will simply have to stay out of public view for the duration of his alleged treatment. Secondly, the President with the head of the security service and the rest of the citizens have so far found themselves existing on Earth in

different times. And this circumstance is already more difficult to overcome.

And there can be only one way out of this situation – the President and the head of the security service, in order to return to the same time in which the rest of the people of the Earth are, need to make a journey into the future (see Fig. 2).

Fig.2. Time-travelling routes of the President and the head of the security service, ensuring the President's return to life after the assassination attempt, as well as the rest of the Earth's inhabitants. The solid lines represent their movements on the surface of the Earth, and the dotted lines represent the movements of the President and the head of security by aeroplane across time zones.

Therefore let's continue. After the President and the head of the security service have solved all their issues in the past time ("d" in Fig. 2), they get on a plane and fly around Antarctica in the opposite direction ("e" in Fig. 2). And thus in 24 hours they return from the past to the present ("d+e" in Fig. 2). And while they are flying, they have time to discuss their problems of the future. And after the plane arrives in the present, the President, together with the head of the security service, secretly gets into a car and leaves for a place of stay chosen on board the plane for the duration of his alleged treatment. And after the completion of this 'healing' ("f" in Fig. 2), the President already appears in his residence. And since the conditions $a + b = g$ and $d + f = h$ were met in such a time travel (see Fig. 2) then, eventually, the President and the head of the security service returned to the same time in which all the other people of the Earth were.

This is how, presumably, the problem of bringing back to life people who have died as a result of an accident or someone else's criminal activity can be solved. But it is not excluded that during the realisation of the solution to this problem, additional circumstances may arise that will require their own solution. And which, hopefully, will turn out to be solvable.

4. Conclusion

The above are just assumptions that need to be verified experimentally. Moreover, these verification experiments are simple, easy to implement and quite convincing. But you need an airplane. And having flown around the North or South Pole through 24 time zones and having made sure that they actually got to the past or future time, the experimenters will get an answer to their question of whether they can actually travel in time. And after that, they can return to their present

time in the manner described above. And if such an experiment confirms the assumptions made in the article, then the above-described and other travel routes to the past and future can be used to solve other problems. For example, simply by asking a passer-by what the date and time are, or by using your iPhone for this purpose. And the knowledge gained in this way can also be used to create more comfortable time machines.

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